

Microlepidoptera of Omsk Region (Russia). Communication 2. Families: Eriocraniidae, Nepticulidae, Opostegidae, Adelidae, Prodoxidae, Incurvariidae, Psychidae, Tineidae, Roeslerstammiidae, Bucculatricidae, Yponomeutidae, Argyresthiidae, Plutellidae, Acrolepiidae, Glyphipterigidae, Ypsolophidae, Lyonetiidae, Bedelliidae, Elachistidae, Parametriotidae, Scythrididae, Momphidae, Blastobasidae, Batrachedridae, Cosmopterigidae, Epermeniidae, Choreutidae

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Abstract

The second communication on the Microlepidoptera fauna of Omsk Region of Russia includes information about 115 species. Most part of them is new to the regional fauna. The list includes 14 species recorded from the Asian part of Russia for the first time, among them *Opostega salaciella* (Treitschke, 1833), *Myrmecozela ochraceella* (Tengström, 1848), *Bucculatrix ulmella* Zeller, 1848,

Euhypnometoides ribesiellus (Joannis, 1900), *Glyphipterix equitella* (Scopoli, 1763), *Mendesia farinella* (Thunberg, 1794), *Elachista humilis* Zeller, 1850, *Elachista littoricola* Le Marchand, 1938, *Elachista pollutella* Duponchel, 1843, *Elachista pullicomella* Zeller, 1839, *Biselachista albidella* (Nylander, 1848), *Scythris flavilaterella* (Fuchs, 1886), *Pyroderces argyrogrammos* (Zeller, 1847), *Epermenia iniquella* (Wocke, 1867).

Keywords

Microlepidoptera, Eriocraniidae, Nepticulidae, Opostegidae, Adelidae, Prodoxidae, Incurvariidae, Psychidae, Tineidae, Roeslerstammiidae, Bucculatricidae, Yponomeutidae, Argyresthiidae, Plutellidae, Acrolepiidae, Glyphipterigidae, Ypsolophidae, Lyonetiidae, Bedelliidae, Elachistidae, Parametriotidae, Scythrididae, Momphidae, Blastobasidae, Batrachedridae, Cosmopterigidae, Epermeniidae, Choreutidae, Omsk Region, West Siberia, new records

Introduction

The present paper is the next contribution in series of papers devoted to studying the Lepidoptera from Omsk Province of Western Siberia. Inventory of this fauna has intensified sharply in the last decade. This made it possible to approach the creation of a regional catalog of Lepidoptera, the first part of which, devoted to Macrolepidoptera, has already been published (Knyazev 2020).

Materials on the Microlepidoptera families (more difficult group as in collecting as in determination) were remained only partially processed. There were some faunistic lists and small additions to them by different Microlepidoptera families published: Gracillariidae (Knyazev et al. 2018, 2019), Coleophoridae (Anikin and Knyazev 2012, 2016, 2021), Ethmiidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012; Knyazev et al. 2015), Depressariidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012, 2013, 2016; Knyazev et al. 2015, 2018, 2019), Cryptolechiidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012), Chimabachidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012), Oecophoridae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012; Knyazev et al. 2015, 2018, 2019), Autostichidae (Lvovsky and Knyazev 2012), Gelechiidae (Ponomarenko and Knyazev 2020), Tortricidae (Dubatolov et al. 2010; Knyazev and Dubatolov 2019), Galacticidae (Knyazev et al. 2016), Pterophoridae (Knyazev and Ustjuzhanin 2013; Knyazev et al. 2018, 2019), Thyrididae (Knyazev et al. 2016), Crambidae (Knyazev et al. 2014, 2016, 2018, 2019; Knyazev and Ponomaryov 2019) и Pyralidae (Knyazev et al. 2014, 2018, 2019). Information on 10 species of Microlepidoptera indicated in the literature, among them *Nemophora degeerella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lavrov, 1927 (as *Adela degeerella*); *Nemophora minimella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775) (Tshugunov, 1911 (as *Nemotois minimellus*); *Lampronia corticella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001 (as *Lampronia rubiella*)); *Psyche casta* (Pallas, 1767) (Lavrov, 1927 (as *Fumea casta*); *Proutia betulina* (Zeller, 1839) (Lavrov, 1927 (as *Fumea betulina*); *Nemapogon granella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Lavrov, 1927; Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001); *Yponomeuta malinella* Zeller, 1838 (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001); *Yponomeuta padella* (Linnaeus, 1758) (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001); *Argyresthia conjugella* Zeller, 1839 (Bogdanov

and Stankovsky, 2001); *Ypsolopha ustella* (Clerck, 1759) (Lavrov, 1927 (as *Cerosotoma radiatella*) needs to be confirmed by new materials due to the impossibility of verifying specimens identifications.

This article presents the results of processing materials for all the other 27 families of Microlepidoptera found in collecting materials. On the other 10 families whose representatives, undoubtedly, should meet in the Omsk region (Micropterigidae, Heliozelidae, Tischeriidae, Douglassiidae, Stathmopodidae, Lypusidae, Chrysopeliidae, Alucitidae, Schreckensteiniidae, Urodidae), we have no materials in collections.

The most part of listed species are reported from the territory of Omsk Region for the first time. These data in a generalized form have already been partially included in the second edition of the Catalog of Lepidoptera of Russia (Sinev 2019). Species firstly reported for the south of West Siberia are marked by an asterisk; species new to the Asian part of Russia – by a double asterisk.

Material and methods

All material processed within the framework of this article was collected on the territory of the Omsk region in the period from 2007 to 2021 by S.A. Knyazev, V.V. Rogalev, S.M. Saikina, V.Yu. Teploukhov and O.N. Kholodov using various light sources. The identification of the material was carried out mainly basing on study of the preparations of male and female genitalia using modern keys and taxonomic revisions for individual families and/or genera. The most part of specimens stored in private collection of S.A. Knyazev (Omsk, Russia), some specimens stored in the Laboratory of Insect Taxonomy of the Zoological Institute of the Russian Academy of Sciences (St. Petersburg, Russia).

Geographical coordinates of the collecting sites:

Amrinskaya Balka – Moskalensky district, 6 km SW of Gvozdevka vill., Amrinskaya Balka, 54°32'23.76"N, 71°47'43.02"E;

Ataichye – Cherlack district, 9 km NE of Dzhartargul' vill., lake Ataichye, 54°27'14.64"N, 75°40'0.39"E;

Atak – Tarsky district, Atak vill., 56°48'24"N, 74°38'36"E;

Atmas – Cherlack district, 2 km N of Malyi Atmas vill., 54°0'48.74"N, 74°56'39.91"E; Atrachi – Tyukalinsky district, 6 km SW Atrachi vill., 55°55'54.34"N, 71°55'5.93"E;

Bogdanovka – Novovarshavsky district, 8 km SE Novovarshavka, 3 km NE Bogdanovka vill., 54°06'32.4"N, 74°46'55.2"E;

Berezka – Isil' kul' sky district, 2 km NE of child camping "Berezka", 55°05'30"N, 71°18'10"E; Berezovka – Azovsky district, Berezovka vill. vicinity, 54°47'52.81"N, 73°4'0.91"E;

Bol'shie Uki – Bol'sheukovsky district, Bol'shie Uki vill., 56°55'37"N, 72°37'37"E;

Buzan – Russko-Polyansky district, 2 km SE of Buzan vill., 53°54'46,46"N, 73°57'51,32"E; Davydovka – Omsk district, 4 km NE of Davydovka vill., 55°11'7,80"N, 73°30'12,36"E;

Ebeity – Moskalensky district, 6 km W of Gvozdevka vill., lake Ebeity, 54°35'27,89"N, 71°47'5,37"E;

Elita – Omsk City, "Elita" gardens, 55°01'48,8"N, 73°32'54,3"E;

Gulyai Pole – Krutinsky district, 44 km NW Krutinka vill., 5 km SW Gulyai Pole vill., 56°13'30,08"N, 70°53'44,58"E;

Karaklinka – Muromtsevsky district, 5 km NE of Karaklinka vill., 56°41'53"N, 75°12'41"E; Keizes – Sedel'nikov district, 8,5 km W of Keizes vill., Stanovaya river, 56°55'13,58"N, 75°34'40,31"E;

Keizes – Sedelnikovskiy district, 8.5 km W of Keizes vill., river Stanovaya, 56°55'13,58"N, 75°34'40,31"E;

Koshkul' – Tyukalinsky district, 0,5 km N of Novyi Koshkul' vill., 56°0'11,34"N, 72°20'42,12"E;

Krasnogorka – Poltavsky district, 8 km NE of Krasnogorka vill., eastern coast of Ebeity lake, 54°35'03,4"N, 71°43'38,3"E;

Krasnoyarka – Omsk district, Krasnoyarka vill., 55°20'0,22"N, 73° 5'33,67"E;

Krasnyi Oktyabr' – Cherlack district, Krasnyi Oktyabr' vill. vicinity, 54°06'59"N, 75°01'01"E; Krutye Luki – Kalatshinsk district, 1.5 km N of Krutye Luki vill., 55°9'39,73"N, 74°52'57,43"E; Leninsk – Okoneshnikovskiy district, 7 km S of Leninsk vill., 54°28'13"N, 75°28'17"E; Listvyagi – Bolsheukovskiy district, Listvyagi vill., 57°14'11,26"N, 71°54'52,42"E;

Maisky – Moskalensky district, 3.5 km NW of Maisky vill., 55°8'37,13"N, 71°43'48,28"E; Merkutly – Kolosovskiy district, 1 km N of Merkutly vill., 56° 6'23,19"N, 72°57'23,23"E; Nalimovo – Nazyvaevskiy district, 2,5 km NW Nalimovo vill., 55°39'23,89"N, 71°47'2,94"E; Nikolaevka – Cherlack district, 8.5 km SE of Nikolaevka vill., 54°12'16,95"N, 75°7'55,70"E; Novovarshavka – Novovarshavskiy district, 3 km E of Novovarshavka vill., river Irtys, 54°10'0,80"N, 74°45'24,81"E;

Okunevo – Muromtsevskiy district, Okunevo vill., 56°26'39,84"N, 74°53'49,29"E; Omsk – Omsk City, 54°59'33"N, 73°16'20"E;

Petropavlovka – Muromtsevskiy district, 1 km W of Petropavlovka vill., 56°24'13,74"N, 75°15'47,94"E;

Podgorodka – Omsk district, 2 km SW of Podgorodka vill., dendropark, 55°8'9,51"N, 73°30'44,27"E;

Russkaya Polyana – Russko-Polyansky district, Russkaya Polyana vill., Park Yubileyniy, 53°46'29,60"N, 73°51'53,91"E;

Samsonovo – Tarskiy district, 9 km N of Tara, 4 km N of Samsonovo vill., 57°0'47,38"N, 74°19'49,44"E;

Sedel'nikov – Sedel'nikovskiy district, 2 km N of Sedel'nikovo, 56°58'22,33"N, 75°17'13,09"E;

Serebryanoye – Gor'kovskiy district, Serebryanoye vill. vicinities, 55°43'0,29"N, 74°20'21,88"E;

Sholacksor – Cherlack district, 10 km SE of Preobrazhenka vill., lake Sholacksor, 54°16'21,24"N, 75°14'42,18"E;

Solntsevka – Isil'kul' district, 5 km N of Solntsevka vill., 55°02'31,79"N, 71°17'18,53"E; Solyanoye – Cherlacksky district, Solyanoye vill., Solyanoye vill., 54°21'4.40"N, 74°38'2.06"E; Tatarka – Cherlack district, 2 km N of Tatarka vill., 53°58'58,47"N, 75°2'1,22"E;

Timshinyakovo – Tarsky district, 0.5 km N of Timshinyakovo vill., 56°57'8,97"N, 74°25'49,51"E;

Ul'zhai – Cherlack district, 6 km SE of Nikolaevka vill., lake Ul'zhai, 54°13'21,90"N, 75°06'59,46"E;

Ust-Ishim – Ust'-Ishim district, 5.5 km NW of Ust'-Ishim vill., Ashair bog, 57°43'01,17"N, 71°03'57,93"E;

Verkhneilyinka – Cherlack district, 2 km NW of Verkhneilyinka vill., 54°33'30.61"N, 74°14'26.02"E;

Yakovlevka – Bolsheukovsky district, 28 km NW of Bolshiye Uki vill., Yakovlevka boundary, river Tevriz, 57°10'38.79"N, 72°25'16.34"E;

Yuryevo – Kormilovsky district, 3 km NW of Yuryevo village, Tarbuga river, 55°10'9.30"N, 74°9'39.39"E.

Results

Below is a list of 115 species of Microlepidoptera, arranged in accordance with the system of the Catalog of Lepidoptera of Russia (Sinev, 2019)

Family *Eriocraniidae*

Eriocrania sangii (Wood, 1891)

Figure 1

Material examined. 2♂, Keizes, 6-7.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂, Davydovka, 5-6.V.2010, S.A. Knyazev.

Eriocrania semipurpurella (Stephens, 1835)

Material examined. 1♂, Timshinyakovo, at light, 18-19.IV.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, Sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, at light, 24-25.IV.2012, S.A. Knyazev.

Eriocrania sparrmannella (Bosc, 1791)

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, 11.V.2008, S.A. Knyazev.

Eriocrania unimaculella (Zetterstedt, 1839)

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Gulyai, Sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, at light, 24- 25.IV.2012, S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 1. *Eriocrania sangii*, Keizes, 6.VI.2018 (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

Family Nepticulidae

****Stigmella obliquella* (Heinemann, 1862)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, 17.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev.

***Stigmella trimaculella* (Haworth, 1828)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, 24.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev.

Family Opostegidae

*****Opostega salaciella* (Treitschke, 1833)**

Material examined. 1♂, Samsonovo, forest: Pinus, Betula, Abies, Larix, Salix, at light, 20- 21.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

Family Adelidae

***Nemophora amatella* (Staudinger, 1892)**

Material examined. 1♂, Listvyagi, 10.VII.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Sedel'nikovo, 6- 7.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1 specimen, Petropavlovka, 23.VI.2007, S.A. Knyazev.

***Nemophora basella* (Eversmann, 1844)**

Material examined. 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 6.VI.2010, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Cherlack rail station, 1.VI.2021, A.G. Moseyko, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

****Nemophora bellela* (Walker, 1863)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, 20.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev.

***Nemophora dumerilella* (Duponchel, 1839)**

Material examined. 5♂, Amrinskaya Balka, 9.VIII.2014, S.A. Knyazev.

***Adela cuprella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775)**

Material examined. 3♂, Gulyai Pole, 25.V.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 7♂, 1♀, Davydovka, 9.V.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, Victory Park, 22.IV.2008, S.A. Knyazev.

***Nematopogon pilella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)**

Material examined. 1♀, Podgorodka, at light, 9-10.VI.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Davydovka, at light, 4-5.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 28-29.V.2017, S.A. Knyazev.

***Nematopogon swammerdamella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. 1♂, Atak, at light, 27.V.2009, S.A. Knyazev.

***Cauchas florella* (Staudinger, 1871)**

Material examined. 1♀, Buzan, at light, 26-27.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

Family **Prodoxidae*****Lampronia capitella* (Clerck, 1759)**

Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001: 22 (as *Incurvaria capitella*).

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 30-31.V.2011, V.Yu. Teploukhov.

****Lampronia fuscata* (Tengström, 1848)**

Material examined. 3♀, Davydovka, at light, 12-13.V.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

Family **Incurvariidae*****Incurvaria pectinea* Haworth, 1828**

Material examined. 3♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', 16.V.2010, S.A. Knyazev.

Family **Psychidae*****Dahlia listrella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, ex larva, 27.IV.2015, S.A. Knyazev.

***Taleporia tubulosa* (Retzius, 1783)**

Material examined. 2 specimens, Sedel'nikovo, 6-7.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 3 specimens, Omsk, at light, 19.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev.

***Rebelia perlucidella* (Bruand, 1853)**

Material examined. 1♂, Ul'zhai, 10-11.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 12- 13.V.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

***Canephora hirsuta* (Poda, 1761)**

(Lavrov, 1927): 74 (as *Pachytelia unicolor*); (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001): 24 (as *Canephora unicolor*).

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, 3.VII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, Okunevo, ex larva, 3.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Petropavlovka, ex larva, 19.VI.2006, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂, Gulyai Pole, ex larva, 20-23.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Podgorodka, 8.VI.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Podgorodka, 19.VI.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂, Davydovka, ex larva, 22-30.VI.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, ex larva, 15.VI.2008, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', ex pupa, 18.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Atmos, at light, 10-11.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev.

***Ptilocephala plumifera* (Ochsenheimer, 1810)**

Chugunov, 1911: 342 (as *Epichnopterix pulla*).

Material examined. 1♂, Solyanoye, 17.V.1989, S.V. Vasilenko.

***Phalacropterix graslinella* (Boisduval, 1852)**

Material examined. 2♂, Gulyai Pole, 31.V.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

***Sterrhopterix fusca* (Haworth, 1809)**

Material examined. 1♂, Yakovlevka, at light, 22-23.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Samsonovo, 20-21.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂, Samsonovo, at light, 17-18.VI.17, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂, Timshinyakovo, at light, 24-25.V.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Sedel'nikov, at light, 6-7.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Okunevo, at light, 30-31.V.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, 19- 20.VI.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, ex larva, 20.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 9♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 22-23.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 13-14.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 5♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 7-8.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Koshkul', at light, 24- 25.VI.2019, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Nalimovo, at light, 20-21.VII.2019, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Maisky, at light, 24-25.VI.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Krasnoyarka, 24.VI.2012, K.B. Ponomarev.

Family Tineidae

****Myrmecozela lutosella* (Eversmann, 1844)**

Material examined. 1♂, Ataichye, at light, 23-24.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Buzan, at light, 11-12.VI.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Myrmecozela ochraceella* (Tengström, 1848)**

Material examined. 1♀, Nikolaevka, at light, 21-22.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Maisky, at light, 24-25.VI.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

***Ateliotum hungaricellum* Zeller, 1839**

Material examined. 1♂, Buzan, at light, 7-8.VIII.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

***Haplotinea insectella* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, VI-VII.2016, V.V. Rogalev.

***Cephimallota praetoriella* (Christoph, 1872)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, 15.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, VII.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Amrinskaya Balka, 6-7.VI.2015, S.A. Knyazev; 5♂♂, Buzan, at light, 26-27.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

***Scardia boletella* (Fabricius, 1794)**

Material examined. 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, at light, 4.VIII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, at light, 16.VII.2012, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, at light, 1-5.VIII.2011, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, at light, 15-23.VI.2012, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, 1♀, Bolshiye Uki, at light, 12.VII.2016, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, Samsonovo, at light, 2-3.VIII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Petropavlovka, at light, 26.VIII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 13-14.VII. 2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 26-27.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Davydovka, 18.VII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 5 specimens, Davydovka, ex larva, 18.VI.2015, S.A. Knyazev.

***Morophaga choragella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775)**

(Lavrov, 1927): 77 (as *Scardia boleti*).

Material examined. 1♂, Samsonovo, at light, 17-18.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 7-8.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 27.VII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, Strelnikova str., at light, 9.VII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, Strelnikova str., at light, 9.VIII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Omsk, at light, 15.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 2♂, Omsk, at light, 15-17.VI.2017, V.V. Rogalev; 1♀, Krasnyi Oktyabr', at light, 6.VI.2010, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Russkaya Polyana, at light, 19.VI.2007, S.A. Knyazev.

****Triaxomera fulvimitrella* (Sodoffsky, 1830)**

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, 12.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

****Archinemapogon yildizae* Koçak, 1981**

Material examined. 2♂♂, Davydovka, at light, 4-5.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, 15.VI.2017, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Elita, ex larva, VII.2021, S.M. Saikina; 1♂, Buzan, at light, 26- 27.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

***Nemapogon cloacella* (Haworth, 1828)**

Material examined. 1♂, Bol'shie Uki vill., at light, VI.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, Podgorodka, at light, 9-10.VI.2014, S.A. Knyazev.

***Nemapogon picarella* (Clerck, 1759)**

Figure 2

Material examined. 1♂, Petropavlovka, at light, 24.VII.2010, S.A. Knyazev; 4 spm., Petropavlovka, at light, 22–23.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina; 1♂, Podgorodka, at light, 16–17.V.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, 17.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, 23.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, 1♀, Omsk, at light, 20–21.VI.2013, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Nikolaevka, at light, 21–22.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Atmas, at light, 6.VII.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Buzan, at light, 11–12.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

***Nemapogon variatella* (Clemens, 1859)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, 15.VI.2017, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', at light, 23.VIII.2009, O.N. Kholodov.

***Trichophaga tapetzella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

(Lavrov, 1927): 77; (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001): 21.

Material examined. 1♂, Amrinskaya Balka, at light, 9–10.VIII.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Nikolaevka, at light, 21–22.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

***Tineola bisselliella* (Hummel, 1823)**

(Lavrov, 1927): 77; (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001): 21.

Material examined. 1♀, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., in the flat, 1.V.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., in the flat, 31.XII.2007, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., in the flat, 29.IV.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂, 2♀, Omsk, Krasnyi Put str., in the flat, 17.III.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 2♀, Omsk, Irtyshskaya naberezhnaya str., in the flat, 17.IV.2009, S.A. Knyazev.

***Tinea bothniella* Svensson, 1953**

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Omsk, at light, 15.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev.

***Tinea columbriella* Wocke, 1877**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., at light, 15.V.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Russia, Omsk City, Zaozernaya str., 27.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Bogdanovka, Irtysh river valley meadow with Salix and Populus, 23.V.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, VII.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, VI–VII.2016, V.V. Rogalev.

***Tinea omichlopis* Meyrick, 1928**

Material examined. 1♂, Atmas vill., meadow with Hippophae, Salix and Populus on the right bank of the river Irtysh, at light, 14.VIII.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Buzan, at light, 16–17.VIII.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

***Tinea pellionella* Linnaeus, 1758**

(Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001): 21.

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Omsk, Strelnikova str., 55°03'09"N, 73°19'28"E, at home, 8.III.2010, S.A. Knyazev.***Niditinea striolella* (Matsumura, 1931)****Material examined.** 1♂, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., 15.IV.2007, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Omsk, at light, VII.2011, V.V. Rogalev.***Monopis crocicapitella* (Clemens, 1859)****Material examined.** 3♂♂, Omsk, at light, VI-VII.2016, V.V. Rogalev.***Monopis laevigella* ([Denis et Schiffermüller], 1775)****Material examined.** 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 4-5.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Okunevo, at light, 30-31.V.2020, S.A. Knyazev.***Monopis monachella* (Hübner, 1796)**(Lavrov, 1927): 77 (as *Blabophanes monachella*).**Material examined.** 1♂, 1♀, Ust-Ishim, at light, 23.VI.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, at light, VIII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 27-28.VIII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Atrachi, at light, 20-21.VIII.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Davydovka, at light, 23.VII.2010, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 11.VI.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Omsk, at light, 5.VI.2017, V.V. Rogalev; 1 spm., Yuryevo, 30-31.VII.2021, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, 2♂♂, Novovarshavka, 29-30.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev; Bogdanovka, at light, 23.V.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', at light, 8.VI.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Nikolaevka, at light, 21- 22.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Atmos, at light, 3.IX.2011, S.A. Knyazev.****Monopis obviella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)****Material examined.** 1♂, Podgorodka, at light, 31.VII.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, 17.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev; 5♂, Omsk, at light, VI-VII.2016, V.V. Rogalev.***Monopis spilotella* (Tengström, 1848)****Material examined.** 1♂, Ust-Ishim, at light, 23.VI.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Sedel'nikov, at light, 6-7.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev.***Monopis weaverella* (Scott, 1858)****Material examined.** 1♀, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., at light, 4.VI.2008, S.A. Knyazev.**Family Roeslerstammiidae*****Roeslerstammia erxlebella* (Fabricius, 1787)****Material examined.** 1♂, Samsonovo, at light, 17-18.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev.

Family **Bucculatricidae**

***Bucculatrix artemisiella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855**

Material examined. 1♂, Buzan, at light, 26-27.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

***Bucculatrix cristatella* (Zeller, 1839)**

Material examined. 1♂, Buzan, at light, 26-27.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

***Bucculatrix humiliella* Herrich-Schäffer, 1855**

Material examined. 1♂, Karaklinka, overwintering moth under the bark, 18.III.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Bucculatrix ulmella* Zeller, 1848**

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 4-5.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev.

Family **Yponomeutidae**

***Yponomeuta evonymella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

(Lavrov, 1927): 77; (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001): 23.

Material examined. 1♂, Bolshiye Uki, at light, 13.VI.2012, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 2♂, Samsonovo, at light, 2-3.VIII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂, Petropavlovka, at light, 25.VII.2010, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, 18.VII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 27.VII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂, Omsk, Neftekhimik gardens, at light, 17.VII.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂, Omsk, Neftekhimik gardens, ex larva, V.V. Rogalev; 7♂, Atmas, meadow with Hippophae, Salix and Populus on the right bank of the river Irtysh, at light, 4 and 27.VII.2011, S.A. Knyazev.

****Yponomeuta vigintipunctatus* (Retzius, 1783)**

Material examined. 1♂, Petropavlovka, at light, 11.VI.2007, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Petropavlovka, at light, 14-15.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Atrachi, at light, 20-21.VIII.2012, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Euhypnometoides ribesiellus* (Joannis, 1900)**

Material examined. 1♀, Petropavlovka, at light, 14-15.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Timshinyakovo, at light, 27.IV.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

****Kessleria fasciapennella* (Stainton, 1849)**

Material examined. 1♂, 2♀♀, Gulyai Pole, Sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, at light, 24-25.IV.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂♂, Keizes, at light, 28.IV.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

***Swammerdamia caesiella* (Hübner, 1796)**

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 4-5.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 2. *Nemapogon picarella*, Petropavlovka, 22.V.2021 (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

****Swammerdamia glaucella* Junnilainen, 2001**

Material examined. 1 ♀, Serebryanoye, at light, 2-3.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev.

****Cedestis gysseleniella* Zeller, 1839**

Material examined. 1 ♂, Omsk, at light, 22.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev.

Family *Argyresthiidae*

***Argyresthia brockeella* (Hübner, 1813)**

Material examined. 1 ♂, Berezka, at light, 5.VII.2010, S.A. Knyazev; 1 ♂, Davydovka, at light, 18.VII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1 ♂, Davydovka, at light, 1.VIII.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1 ♂, Davydovka, at light, 6-7.VII.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 2 ♂, Omsk, at light, VII.2011, V.V. Rogalev.

Family *Plutellidae*

***Plutella xylostella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

(Lavrov, 1927): 77; (Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001): 23.

Material examined. 1 ♂, Yakovlevka, at light, 20-21.V.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 2 ♂♂, Bolshiye Uki, at light, VI.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1 ♂, Petropavlovka, at light, 26.V.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1 ♂, Atak, at light, 27.V.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1 ♂, Gulyai

Pole, 25.V.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Merkutly, in twilight, 1.VI.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, 30.V.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂♂, 2♀♀, Davydovka, in twilight, 10.V.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Davydovka, in UV light trap, 12.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 11.VI.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1 specimen, Davydovka, at light, 2.VI.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1 specimen, Davydovka, in twilight, 10.V.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Omsk, at light, VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 2♂♂, Omsk, at light, 17.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, VI-VII.2016, V.V. Rogalev; 1♀, Omsk, at light, 2.VI.2017, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Berezovka, at light, 6-7.VIII.2021, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Verkhneilyinka, at light, 1.IX.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Ul'zhai, at light, 10-11.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', at light, 8.VI.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Atmas, 14.VIII.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Tatarka, at light, 19-20.IV.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Buzan, at light, 14.IX.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

Family Acrolepiidae

Acrolepiopsis assectella (Zeller, 1839)

Material examined. 1♂, Gulyai Pole, Sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, at light, 24-25.IV.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Tatarka, tree planting along the road with Populus, Betula, Malus, at light, 14-15.IV.2012, S.A. Knyazev.

Family Glyphipterigidae

***Glyphipterix equitella* (Scopoli, 1763)

Material examined. 1♂, 5♀♀, Ust-Ishim, 7-8.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

**Glyphipterix haworthana* (Stephens, 1834)

Material examined. 1♂, 2♀♀, Ust-Ishim, 7-8.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Gulyai Pole, Sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, 25.V.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

Family Ypsolophidae

Ypsolopha asperella (Linnaeus, 1761)

Figure 3

Material examined. 1♀, Timshinyakovo, at light, 18-19.IV.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1 specimen, Keizes, at light, visual registration, 28.IV.2021, S.A. Knyazev; 4♀♀, Podgorodka, at light, 16-17.V.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Podgorodka, at light, 29.IV.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Davydovka, at light, 20.IV.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 1 specimen, Omsk, Victory Park, 27.X.2006, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Omsk, Krasnyi Put' str., at light, 10-13.V.2011, O.E. Kosterin; 1♀, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., at light, 6.V.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂♂, 4♀♀, Omsk, OmGAU Park, overwintering moths under the bark, 9.I.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 4♂♂, 1♀, Omsk, at light, 11-15.IV.2012, V.V. Rogalev; 1♀, Omsk, at light, 23.VI.2017, V.V. Rogalev; 1♀, Atmas, at light, 6.VII.2011, S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 3. *Ypsolopha asperella*, Omsk, Park of Omsk State Agrarian University, overwintering moth under the tree bark, 8.I.2018 (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

****Ypsolopha falcella* ([Denis & Schiffermüller], 1775)**

Material examined. 1 ♀, Podgorodka, at light, 1.VIII.2014, S.A. Knyazev.

***Ypsolopha instabilella* (Mann, 1866)**

Material examined. 1 ♂, Buzan, at light, 14.IX.2020, S.A. Knyazev; 1 ♀, Tatarka vill., at light, 20.IX.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

****Ypsolopha nemorella* (Linnaeus, 1758)**

Material examined. 1 ♂, Podgorodka, at light, 31.VII.2014, S.A. Knyazev.

****Ypsolopha parenthesesella* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Figure 4

Material examined. 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Petropavlovka, at light, 6.IX.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1 ♂, 1 ♀, Keizes, at light, 13.IX.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

***Ypsolopha scabrella* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined. 1 ♀, Petropavlovka, at light, 6.IX.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

***Ochsenheimeria urella* Fischer von Röslerstamm, 1842**

Material examined. 1 ♂, Krasnyi Oktyabr', at light, 16.V.2010, S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 4. *Ypsolopha parenthesesella*, Petropavlovka, 6.IX.2018 (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

Family Lyonetiidae

Lyonetia clerkella (Linnaeus, 1758)

(Bogdanov and Stankovsky, 2001): 24.

Material examined. 1♀, Ust-Ishim, 7-8.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Mezhevnaya, overwintering moth under the bark, 18.III.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

**Lyonetia ledi* Wocke, 1859

Material examined. 1♂, Podgorodka, 31.VII.2014, S.A. Knyazev.

Family Bedelliidae

Bedellia somnulentella (Zeller, 1847)

Figure 5

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, 3.X.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, 1.XI.2020, S.M. Saikina; 1♀, Krasnyi Oktyabr`, 18.IX.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 5 spm., Atmos, 21.IX.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Buzan, 14-15.VIII.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂♂, Buzan, at light, 5.V.2021, S.A. Knyazev, S.M. Saikina.

Family Elachistidae

***Mendesia farinella* (Thunberg, 1794)

Material examined. 1♀, Omsk, at light, 15-16.VI.2012, V.V. Rogalev.

***Elachista anserinella* Zeller, 1839**

Material examined. 3♂♂, Bogdanovka, Irtysh river valley meadow with Salix and Populus, at light, 23.V.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, 12.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 4-5.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Podgorodka, twilight, 26.V.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂♂, Buzan, at light, 11-12.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

****Elachista fasciola* Parenti, 1983**

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, meadow near Betula groves, 30.V.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Ebeity, 17.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Elachista humilis* Zeller, 1850**

Material examined. 1♀, Koshkul', 25.VI.2019, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Elachista littoricola* Le Marchand, 1938**

Material examined. 1♀, Solntsevka, near road with Ulmus, 16.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

***Elachista maculicerusella* Bruand, 1859**

Material examined. 1♀, Atmas, meadow with Hippophae, Salix and Populus on the right bank of the river Irtysh, 14.VIII.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Bol'shie Uki, at light, VIII.2013, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 1♂, Nikolaevka, at light, 21-22.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 5. *Bedellia somnulentella* (dark melanic form), Omsk, Elita, 1.XI.2020, S.M. Saikina leg. (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

*****Elachista pollutella* Duponchel, 1843**

Material examined. 1♂, Krasnogorka, steppe, at light, 18.V.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂♂, Ul'zhai, 10.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Buzan, at light, 11-12.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Elachista pullicomella* Zeller, 1839**

Material examined. 2♂♂, Buzan, at light, 11-12.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

****Elachista rudectella* Stainton, 1851**

Material examined. 1♀, Omsk, at light, 15.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Buzan, at light, 11- 12.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂♂, Buzan, at light, 18-19.V.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

****Elachista spumella* Caradja, 1920**

Material examined. 2♂♂, Ul'zhai, 10.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂♂, Buzan, at light, 11- 12.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

****Elachista subalbidella* Schläger, 1847**

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 19.VI.2008, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Biselachista albidella* (Nylander, 1848)**

Material examined. 1♂, Ataichye, at light, 3-4.VI.2014, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Nikolae-vka, at light, 21-22.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

****Biselachista utonella* (Frey, 1856)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, VI-VII.2016, V.V. Rogalev.

****Cosmiotes freyerella* (Hübner, 1825)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, V.V. Rogalev.

Family **Parametriotidae**

***Heinemannia laspeyrella* (Hübner, 1796)**

Material examined. 1♀, Petropavlovka, at light, 3-4.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev.

Family **Scythrididae**

****Scythris clavella* (Zeller, 1855)**

Material examined. 1♂, Sholacksor, at light, 19-20.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Leninsk, steppe, 16.VII.2011, S.A. Knyazev.

*****Scythris flavilaterella* (Fuchs, 1886)**

Material examined. 1♂, Gulyai Pole vill., meadow near Sphagnum swamp with pinus, Betula, Ledum, 22.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Sedel'nikovo, pine forest with Betula, Tremula, Salix, at light, 6-7.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

****Scythris mikkolai* Sinev, 1993**

Material examined. 1♂, Atmas, meadow with Hippophae, Salix and Populus on the right bank of the river Irtysh, 8.VII.2011, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, V.V. Rogalev.

****Scythris minorella* Sinev, 2001**

Material examined. 1♂, Ataichye, at light, 23-24.VI.2014, S.A. Knyazev.

***Scythris obscurella* (Scopoli, 1763)**

Material examined. 1♂, Gulyai Pole, at light, 19-20.VI.2012, S.A. Knyazev; 2♂♂, Bol'shie Uki vill., at light, 1-15.VI.2012, V.Yu. Teploukhov; 2♂♂, Sedel'nikovo, pine forest with Betula, Tremula, Salix, at light, 6-7.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Samsonovo vill., forest: Pinus, Betula, Abies, Larix, Salix, at light, 20-21.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

****Scythris sinensis* (R.Felder et Rogenhofer, 1875)**

Material examined. 1♂, Krutyte Luki, 20.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, 1♀, Elita, in copula, 10.VI.2020, S.M. Saikina leg.

Family *Batrachedridae*****Batrachedra praeangusta* (Haworth, 1828)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, VII.2011, V.V. Rogalev.

Family *Momphidae*****Cyphophora idaei* (Zeller, 1839)**

Material examined. 1♂, Sedel'nikovo, forest: Pinus, Betula, Tremula, Salix, at light, 6-7.VII.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

****Mompha glaucella* Sinev, 1986**

Material examined. 1♀, Russia, Omsk, Prospekt Mira str., 18.IV.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 3♂♂, Gulyai Pole, meadow near Sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, 23.IX.2013, S.A. Knyazev.

***Mompha sturnipennella* (Treitschke, 1833)**

Figure 6

Material examined. 1♀, Gulyai Pole, meadow near Sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, 23.IX.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Samsonovo, 10.I.2018, overwintering moth under the bark, S.A. Knyazev.

Family **Blastobasidae**

****Hypatopa binotella* (Thunberg, 1794)**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, V.V. Rogalev; 1♀, Atmas, meadow with Hippophae, Salix and Populus on the right bank of the river Irtysh, 8.VII.2016, S.A. Knyazev.

Family **Cosmopterigidae**

***Pancalia leuwenhoekella* (Linnaeus, 1761)**

Material examined. 1♀, Petropavlovka, at light, 14-15.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev.

****Cosmopterix orichalcea* Stainton, 1861**

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, 9.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev.

***Cosmopterix sibirica* Sinev, 1985**

Material examined. 4♂♂, Davydovka, at light, 4-5.VI.2016, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 28-29.V.2017, S.A. Knyazev.

****Linnaecia phragmitella* Stainton, 1851**

Material examined. 1♀, Omsk, Zaozernaya str., at light, 28.VII.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, 15.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev.

*****Pyroderces argyrogrammos* (Zeller, 1847)**

Material examined. 1♀, Omsk, at light, 24.VI.2015, V.V. Rogalev.

****Eteobalea anonymella* (Riedl, 1965)**

Material examined. 4♂♂, Gulyai Pole, sphagnum swamp with Pinus, Betula, Ledum, at UV- light trap, 23.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Serebryanoye, at light, 2-3.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; 4♂♂, 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 6.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Sholacksor, at light, 19- 20.VI.2017, S.A. Knyazev; Davydovka, at light, 19.VI.2008, S.A. Knyazev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, 9.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, 25.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Buzan, at light, 11-12.VI.2018, S.A. Knyazev.

***Eteobalea tririvella* (Staudinger, 1871)**

Material examined. 1♂, Davydovka, at light, 18.VII.2009, S.A. Knyazev; 4♂♂, Omsk, at light, 9-15.VI.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Atmas, at light, 7-8.VII.2016, S.A. Knyazev.

Figure 6. *Mompha sturnipennella*, Samsonovo, overwintering moth under the tree bark, 20.I.2018 (photo by S.A. Knyazev).

Family Epermeniidae

Epermenia illigerella (Hübner, 1813)

Material examined. 3♂♂, 1♀, Samsonovo, forest: Pinus, Betula, Abies, Larix, Salix, at light, 20-21.VI.2013, S.A. Knyazev; 1♀, Davydovka, at light, 6-7.VII.2020, S.A. Knyazev.

***Epermenia iniquella* (Wocke, 1867)

Material examined. 1♂, 1♀, Omsk, at light, VII.2011, V.V. Rogalev; 1♀, Omsk, at light, 16.VII.2015, V.V. Rogalev; 1♂, Omsk, at light, VI-VII.2016, V.V. Rogalev.

**Epermenia strictella* (Wocke, 1867)

Material examined. 1♀, Podgorodka, at light, 5.X.2019, S.A. Knyazev.

Family Choreutidae

**Prochoreutis sehestediana* (Fabricius, 1776)

Material examined. 1♂, Omsk, at light, 18-19.VI.2013, V.V. Rogalev.

Choreutis diana (Hübner, 1822)

Material examined. 1♀, Atmas, 27.VII.2011, S.A. Knyazev.

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